

Table 1: Barriers, effects, suggestions and article links

Barriers	Effects	Suggestions	Link	ID
Being the only woman, lack of encouragement, male dominance	Forced maturation, change in perspective, unconscious bias, Impostor syndrome, feeling of pain	Seek security, ignore, appropriate responses, consider constructive criticism, female connections on social media, continuous learning, ask for help, participate in technology events, have a "code friend", never underestimate yourself, let your work be a reflection of you, letting people know that you are a developer	dev.to/asayerio_techblog/programming-as-a-woman-in-tech-2a15	A1
Most people are men, unequal salaries	Behaving like a boy, adapting to other people's vision, exhausting and challenging	Don't change yourself under pressure, master your skills, evaluate the company culturally, negotiate salaries, companies with women as mentors, don't feel influenced by prejudice, look for positions that challenge you	dev.to/ilonacodes/what-i-wish-as-a-woman-in-tech-i-knew-early-on-kpc	A2
Exclusion, lack of recognition, lack of professional advancement	Being ridiculed	Change jobs	dev.to/jesssolka/reflections-on-my-career-as-a-woman-in-tech-319e	A3
Prejudice	Anger	Consider evolution	dev.to/mim/because-you-are-a-woman-2393	A4
Labeling, lack of professional recognition, underestimating	Shaken confidence, Pretending lack of ability, sadness, Being misunderstood	Consider developments, do not remain silent, the manager needs to be aware	dev.to/heyjtk/the-typecast-tango-avoiding-the-frontend-label-as-a-woman-in-tech-5a6m	A5
Toxic masculinity, stereotypes, few trans women	Language replication, pain	N/a	dev.to/penelope_zone/the-incredible-weight-of-being-a-trans-woman-in-tech-45n0	A6
Search for visibility, prejudice, exclusions, microaggressions	Invisibility, impotence and exhaustion, contempt and pain, shaken mental health	Presence of an "ally"	dev.to/eevajonnapanula/sometimes-i-feel-like-im-invisible-experiences-of-a-woman-in-tech-3glb	A7
Stereotypes	N/a	N/a	dev.to/eevajonnapanula/sometimes-i-feel-like-im-invisible-experiences-of-a-woman-in-tech-3glb	A8

Continues in the next page

Barriers	Effects	Suggestions	Link	ID
Male dominance	Loneliness, doubt and frustration	Various professional areas, find a good mentor, progression above perfection, learn when to rest, embrace failure, continuous learning, document your journey, kill self-doubt imposter syndrome, speak up, build a support system, be patient, find out what motivates you, embrace failure, get social, consistency	dev.to/emmadonery/being-a-woman-in-tech-my-journey-1mo8	A9
Few women ready for the market	N/a	Leadership, encouragement, investing in education for women	dev.to/marinaserranomontes/yes-i-am-a-developer-and-yes-i-am-a-woman-4f8f	A10
Ageism	N/a	Never give up	dev.to/studiomsong/be-a-yes-woman-2m3h	A11
Lack of recognition, lack of role models, impostor syndrome	Lack of confidence	Support systems, being a role model, not being afraid of failure, highlighting your strengths, mentoring other people, not being afraid of asking questions	dev.to/codementor/what-it-means-to-be-a-women-in-tech-in-2019-4el6	A12
Feeling stupid, exclusion, devaluation	N/a	N/a	https://dev.to/hbalenda/nevertheless-it-still-sucks-to-be-a-woman-in-tech-1ghh	A13
Lack of confidence in female potential, not being invited to meetings	Discouragement, overcoming, scared of entering the area	N/a	https://dev.to/sugarcoded/so-this-what-it-s-like-being-a-woman-in-tech-432o	A14
Invisibility	N/a	N/a	dev.to/mcampourcy/the-first-french-computer-science-thesis-author-was-a-woman-but-nobody-knows-ho7	A15
Aggressive work environment	N/a	N/a	dev.to/sabrinasuarezarrieta/developer-world-as-a-woman-2h6l	A16
Salary disparity	N/a	N/a	dev.to/educative/hercode-tips-for-negotiating-compensation-as-a-woman-in-tech-50bl	A17
Male dominance	N/a	Participate in open-source projects	dev.to/dellamora/boosting-woman-participation-in-open-source-projects-a-beginners-guide-to-contributing-5g49	A18
Gender prejudice, lack of equality between genders	N/a	Stop comparing, don't be ashamed, women helping women, be proud of what you have achieved	dev.to/techlorean/career-in-tech-why-bother-if-you-re-female-1pa4	A19
Lack of appreciation, role stereotypes, male dominance, ageism, difficulty in career progression, prejudice in the hiring process	Fewer women leaders receive less credit	Promoting equity	dev.to/stateofdevnation/on-the-role-of-female-coders-in-software-development-3nii	A20

Continues in the next page

Barriers	Effects	Suggestions	Link	ID
Male dominance, ES seems to be complicated, only woman on the team, Lack of help, being treated differently, afraid to ask questions	Discrimination, loneliness, invisibility and lack of support, lack of help	Ask questions, remain professional, have more female support, be confident in your skills and knowledge, give your opinion	dev.to/duomly/how-is-it-to-be-a-female-programmer-in-the-tech-world-341c	A21
Job description, sexism, Insecurity	Personality change, fear of failure, prejudice, rejection	Change in recruitment processes	dev.to/char,one/could - your - recruitment - process - be - discouraging - female - developers - 4pch	A22
Masculine dominance, being able to identify as a developer, unconscious bias hostile work environment, female minority, not feeling able	Pressure, anxieties and anguish, difficulty in seeing oneself as a developer, lack of confidence	Avoid sexism, have confidence	dev.to/rizz0s/persisting-past-dissonance-adapting-to-the-identity-of-a-female-developer-4413	A23
Underestimation, role stereotypes, insecurity, proof of knowledge	Underestimation, generation of stereotypes, passive aggression, impostor syndrome and lack of confidence, unconscious bias	Female role models, diversity in workplaces, avoiding assumptions, accepting mistakes	dev.to/whatminjacodes/4-annoyances-of-being-a-female-developer-and-how-to-help-making-it-better-2ckg	A24
Sexism, lack of respect, difficulty in entrepreneurship	Acceptance of rejection, misogyny, humiliation	Support and empathy, never stop believing in yourself, impose yourself	dev.to/rhiannonmonks/what-it-s-like-to-be-a-technical-female-founder-of-a-mobile-app-5pk	A25
Few women	N/a	Disclosure of the advantages of diverse teams, female networking, recognition of competence, hiring more women, promoting professional development, providing a clear profile description, investing in training for women	dev.to/studio_m_s_ong/taking - the - perspective - of - a - female - dev - 581m	A26
Female underrepresentation, male dominance, bias in hiring	Lack of female representation, Lack of career progression	Reduction of prejudice and incentives in the hiring process, use blind hiring techniques, promote inclusive culture, female opportunities, organizational awareness, encourage more women, motivate women to study disciplines related to exact sciences	dev.to/blueoptima/why-are-there-so-few-female-software-developers-4e47	A27

Continues in the next page

Barriers	Effects	Suggestions	Link	ID
Male dominance, lack of women in IT to share, no negotiation, internal pressure, exclusion, stereotypes, lack of recognition, sexism	Excessive caution, pay gap, panic attacks, subtle abuse, lack of recognition	Avoid 100% male interviewers, offer flexibility, open and collaborative culture, - equivalent salary, identify problems	dev.to/ilonacodes/being-a-female-programmer-how-is-it-for-you-i7d	A28
Female minority, difficulty entering the job market, reasons for giving up a career, sexism, stereotypes, men are more prone to the area	N/a	N/a	dev.to/annietaylorchen/why-are-there-less-female-developers-1d3d	A29
Male dominance, lack of respect and harassment, cultural pressure, discouragement, lack of visibility	Overcoming, harassment and lack of respect	Innovative job selections, flexible hours and remote work, having a good organizational culture	dev.to/maria_michou/why-do-we-have-more-male-applicants-than-female-ones-32c7	A30
Male dominance, lack of family support, toxic messages	N/a	Visibility, promotion of female work, mentoring, encouraging from childhood	dev.to/devdrake0/what-must-we-do-to-encourage-more-female-coders-155a	A31
Male dominance, ageism, lack of career promotion, lack of advancement, AI penalizes women's resumes	N/a	Supporting the success of women in technology, encouraging companies	dev.to/thisdotmedia/the-future-of-ai-is-female-how-hiring-bias-mitigation-in-nlp-can-be-great-for-women-now-and-in-the-future-7fm	A32
Male dominance, prejudice	Impostor syndrome	No one knows everything, have a support group	dev.to/eevajonnapanula/5-things-i-ve-learned-as-a-female-developer-p19	A33
Gender disparity	N/a	N/a	dev.to/kinas/becoming-a-female-software-engineer-who-studied-geography-3nmm	A34
Being heard, stereotypes	N/a	Take risks, however you want, be heard, assertive communication	dev.to/aliracoffinan/to-the-young-female-software-engineer-with-her-first-job-offer-4f4o	A35
Exclusion, struggle for acceptance	Feeling scared	N/a	dev.to/studio_m_song/things-a-female-dev-who-has-been-in-the-industry-for-16-years-has-to-say-2li3	A36
Conciliate	N/a	Constant learning, set limits and delegate tasks, ask for help, look for synergy, communicate clearly about your needs, redefine your victories, let go of blame, stay focused	dev.to/educative/6-tips-finding-your-balance-as-a-mother-and-software-engineer-47mn	A37
Lack of female leadership	N/a	Gender diversity in companies, gender equity, training to deal with diversity	dev.to/kaviiiisha/promoting-gender-equity-and-inclusion-in-the-tech-industry-and-beyond-4lic	A38

Continues in the next page

Barriers	Effects	Suggestions	Link	ID
Pay gap, discrimination	Lack of confidence	N/a	dev.to/whoisnamdi/how-age-race-and-gender-affect-software-engineering-pay-59jo	A39
Lack of diversity, stereotypes and prejudices, lack of representation, workplace culture, poor hiring, compensation and promotion practices	Discouraged from following the area, they do not feel like they belong	Address stereotypes and biases, increase representation of women in the industry, promote inclusive workplace cultures, implement fair hiring practices and enable equal pay and advancement opportunities, offer mentoring and training programs, address unconscious biases, and promote the balance between personal and professional life.	dev.to/sayururehan/gender-equality-in-tech-breaking-barriers-and-building-a-better-future-3ho9	A40
Male dominance	N/a	Educate yourself, don't assume people's pronouns, recognize your privileges and bring diversity to the table, be patient with yourself, take action and speak up	dev.to/dionarodrigues/i-am-proud-to-be-a-transgender-it-developer-okh	A41
Recognition	N/a	N/a	https://dev.to/calikat68/transgender-tech-o7i	A42
Male dominance	Lack of empathy	Normalization of motherhood in tech	dev.to/erikaheidi/normalizing-maternity-in-tech-2oe9	A43
Always being responsible for sacrifices, not being able to work overtime, parental responsibilities, being a minority	It is only up to the mother to be absent from work, for fear of becoming out of date	Remote work, no time micromanagement	dev.to/rose/women-in-tech-being-a-developer-and-a-mom-gcf	A44
Stereotypes, Devaluation of women	Abandonment	Valuation of women, Promote inclusive culture, Recognize your skills, Change recruitment processes, Be a role model/advertise, Build a support system, both to help others and to be helped, Invest in training for women, Change recruitment processes	www.infoq.com/news/2022/03/tight-cohesive-tech-teams/	A45
Stereotypes, Devaluation of women	Lack of female representation	Invest in training for women	www.infoq.com/news/2016/06/lack-women-in-tech/	A46
Gender disparity	Change in the perspective of the environment / the presence of women is always noticed	Inclusive organizational culture	www.infoq.com/news/2014/10/west/	A47

Continues in the next page

Barriers	Effects	Suggestions	Link	ID
Lack of recognition, Undervaluation, Sexism	Bias	Changing Recruitment Processes	www.infoq.com/news/2016/11/thoughtworks-women-friendly/	A48
Female Devaluation	N/a	Changing Recruitment Processes	www.infoq.com/news/2016/11/managing-men-women/	A49
Stereotypes, Sexism, Male Dominance	N/a	Inclusive Organizational Culture	www.infoq.com/articles/book-review-good-guys/	A50
Sexism, Exclusion	N/a	Attending Tech Events, Being a Role Model/Spreading the Word	www.infoq.com/articles/book-review-good-guys/	A51
Sexism, Stereotypes, Microaggressions	N/a	N/a	www.infoq.com/news/2018/12/future-work-female/	A52
Underrepresentation	Imposter Syndrome, Underrepresentation of women, Acceptance, Overcoming	Recognizing your abilities, Being a role model/disclosing	www.infoq.com/articles/breaking-barriers-open-source/	A53
Ageism A54	Bias	Ignoring Bias	Imposter Syndrome, Inclusive Organizational Culture, Building a support system, both to help others and to be helped	www.infoq.com/enterprise/2018/02/entrepren-thrive-tech/
Undervaluation	N/a	N/a	www.infoq.com/presentations/women-hiring-inclusivity/	A55
Male Dominance, Feminine Devaluation, Stereotypes	Imposter Syndrome, Preventing Women from Entering the Field	Encouraging Sisterhood	www.infoq.com/presentations/managing-men-women//	A56
Male Dominance	N/a	N/a	www.infoq.com/presentations/women-ai-blockchain/	A57
Male Dominance	N/a	Be a Role Model / Spread the Word, Build a Support System, Both to Help Others and to Be Helped	www.infoq.com/presentations/women-agile//	A58
Male Dominance	Bias	N/a	www.infoq.com/presentations/cs-culture-history/	A59
Stereotypes	N/a	N/a	www.infoq.com/presentations/women-agile-confidence/	A60
Male Dominance, Gender Disparity	Imposter Syndrome	Recognizing Your Skills, Recognizing Your Skills, Being a Role Model / Promoting	www.infoq.com/presentations/women-programming/	A61
Male Dominance, Gender Disparity	Emotional Exhaustion	Recognizing Your Skills, Recognizing Your Skills, Being a Role Model / Promoting, -Changing Recruitment Processes	www.infoq.com/presentations/diversity-inclusion-panel/	A62
End of Table				